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2 **Abrupt changes in the subpolar North Atlantic and their impact on the climate of the British Isles**

3 Matthew B Menary^{1,*}, Laura C Jackson¹, Richard A. Wood¹, Richard A. Betts^{1,2}

4 1. Met Office Hadley Centre, FitzRoy Road, Exeter, EX1 3PB, UK

5 2. Global Systems Institute, University of Exeter, North Park Road, Exeter, EX4 4QE

6 *Now at: European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts, Shinfield Park, Reading, RG2
7 9AX, UK

8

9 **Abstract**

10 There has been increasing interest in the possibility of abrupt climatic changes in the North Atlantic
11 and their impacts on northwestern Europe. Here, we investigate such abrupt changes in a large
12 ensemble of CMIP6 climate models. We define two potentially observable metrics based on subpolar
13 sea surface temperatures (SSTs) or mixed layer depths (MLDs), to explore the link between
14 temperature changes and convection collapse. The two metrics yield similar numbers of abrupt
15 events but suggest that several types of abrupt event are possible. Abrupt MLD changes appear
16 related to ongoing warming. Abrupt SST changes mostly consist of decadal cooling followed by
17 warming, apparently related to coupled dynamics involving the NAO. Models with more realistic NAO
18 variability show more such events. However, several more persistent SST events are also found. Both
19 cooling and warming phases have important implications for impacts and adaptation, particularly
20 over the British Isles.

21 **Plain language summary**

22 There is increasing interest in sudden climate changes in the North Atlantic and how these changes
23 might affect Europe. This study uses a large set of recent climate models to see if these sudden
24 changes are likely. We use two measures related to 1) sea surface temperatures (SSTs) and 2) mixed
25 layer depths (MLDs) to study the connection between surface temperatures and the collapse of
26 oceanic convection. Both measures show similar numbers of sudden changes, but they don't seem to
27 be related. Sudden MLD changes mostly seem to be connected to ongoing global warming. Sudden
28 SST changes mostly follow a pattern of cooling and warming over around 20 years, apparently linked
29 to the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO). Models which have better NAO variability have more chance
30 of a sudden change in SST. A few SST events persist over several decades. These cooling and warming
31 phases could have significant effects, especially for the British Isles, and need to be considered when
32 planning climate change adaptation.

33 **Main points**

- 34 1. The North Atlantic shows the potential for abrupt changes in sea surface temperature linked
35 to decadal variability in coupled processes
- 36 2. The abrupt cooling and subsequent warming may have significant implications for impacts
37 and adaption, particularly over the British Isles
- 38 3. Using observational constraints, the model-derived likelihood of an abrupt change in North
39 Atlantic temperatures approximately doubles.

40 **1 Introduction**

41 The subpolar North Atlantic (SPNA) region is a critical component of the global climate system,
42 influencing climate variability on annual to decadal timescales (Gastineau & Frankignoul, 2015;
43 Sutton & Hodson, 2005; Yeager, 2015), with significant implications for temperature and salinity
44 distribution (Holliday et al., 2018; Marzocchi et al., 2015). The SPNA gyre circulation is also crucial in
45 driving decadal climate variability and potentially exhibits multiple circulation modes (Born &
46 Mignot, 2012; Born & Stocker, 2014).

47 The North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) also plays a significant role in SPNA variability through
48 associated changes in heat fluxes and winds. In the mid-1990s, the SPNA underwent a rapid
49 warming, with SSTs increasing by around 1°C in just 2 years (Sarafanov et al., 2008). This warming
50 followed a prolonged positive phase of the NAO, followed by an unusually negative NAO index. This
51 rapid warming is consistent with a delayed response to the prolonged positive phase NAO, and not
52 simply an instantaneous response to the negative NAO (Robson et al., 2012).

53 Other notable historic shifts in the SPNA climate system include the possibility that sea-ice to ocean
54 feedbacks sustained an initial cooling into the Little Ice Age by weakening the SPNA gyre circulation
55 (Moreno-Chamarro et al., 2017). Empirical evidence from annually resolved bivalve proxy records
56 from the North Icelandic shelf shows that the SPNA climate system destabilised during two episodes
57 prior to the Little Ice Age, potentially indicating a system approaching an abrupt transition (Arellano-
58 Nava et al., 2022).

59 In climate model projections, the SPNA is the epicentre of the so called “warming hole” (a relative
60 cooling), which has been linked to changes in the strength of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning
61 Circulation (AMOC) due to weakening deep convection (Menary & Wood, 2018). Anomalous cooling
62 in this region has been linked to changes in Atlantic hurricane frequency (Smith et al., 2010) and an
63 increase in summer precipitation over Europe (Dong et al., 2013). In addition, some models exhibit
64 significant temperature drops over the North Atlantic that have been associated with a more
65 complete collapse of SPNA convection (Sgubin et al., 2017; Swingedouw et al., 2021). Such
66 temperature drops may be a symptom of the region undergoing a rapid, sustained, and self-
67 perpetuating change known as a tipping point (Armstrong McKay et al., 2022) Weighting climate
68 models based on the fidelity of their ocean stratification in this region significantly increases the
69 estimated risk of an abrupt cooling (Sgubin et al. 2017, Swingedouw et al., 2021). The associated
70 “cold waves” may have significant repercussions over Europe, including impacts on viticulture
71 (Sgubin et al., 2019).

72 One mechanism proposed for abrupt changes in the SPNA involves feedbacks between surface
73 salinity, deep convection, and subpolar gyre circulation, with the latter hypothesised to feedback on
74 surface salinity (Born and Mignot 2012, Born and Stocker 2014). Born et al (2013) studied this
75 mechanism in CMIP3-generation climate models, finding that while it operated in some models, it
76 was not universally present, and other processes may be at play for some abrupt SPNA events. Gu et
77 al (2024), analysing a large, single-model ensemble, proposed two further mechanisms leading to
78 alternative states of the SPNA, both still involving convection changes, while Born et al (2013) and
79 Sgubin et al (2017) found some events that did not appear to primarily involve a convective
80 feedback.

81 Understanding potential abrupt changes in the SPNA is crucial for developing effective strategies to
82 mitigate and adapt to climate change risks. However, the current level of understanding is limited,
83 with more than one mechanism proposed. Interpretation of the literature is further complicated by
84 differing choices of how to define abrupt events (e.g. in terms of gyre strength (Born et al 2013) or
85 sea surface temperature (Sgubin et al. 2017, Swingedouw et al. 2021)). In this paper we adopt two

86 pragmatic definitions, based on decadal surface temperature or mixed layer changes of a particular
87 magnitude, that are not based on a particular hypothesised mechanism. We use such events,
88 diagnosed across the CMIP6 model ensemble, to ask whether there is a robust connection between
89 abrupt SST and mixing changes. We further assess regional climatic anomalies associated with SPNA
90 events in the context of ongoing climate change, using the British Isles as an example of a region
91 likely to be strongly affected.

92 **2 Methods**

93 In this analysis we use data from all available CMIP6 climate models (Eyring et al., 2016) that
94 provided data for the historical simulations or future projections using scenarios SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5,
95 SSP3-7.0, or SSP5-8.5 (Supp. Table 1). We use all available ensemble members, analysing a total of
96 775 simulations covering 90195 model years. Mixed layer depths (MLDs, defined as in Griffies et al,
97 2016), mean sea level pressure (MSLP), and the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) index are calculated
98 as wintertime (January to March inclusive) means, whilst other variables are calculated as annual
99 means. For comparisons to observations, we use surface air temperature (SAT) reconstructions from
100 the gridded BEST dataset (Rohde & Hausfather, 2020), station-based sea level pressure observations
101 from HadSLP2 (Allan & Ansell, 2006), and precipitation reconstructions from GPCC (Becker et al.,
102 2013).

103 Previously, Swingedouw et al. (2021; hereafter SW21) defined abrupt events in the SPNA in terms of
104 decadal changes in SSTs. We use a similar method, defining an abrupt SST event as a 1 Kelvin
105 reduction in SPNA area-averaged SST from any given decade to the next, over at least 50% of this
106 region shown in Supp. Figure 1. A hypothesis when abrupt SPNA changes are defined in this way is
107 that they are associated with an abrupt change, or collapse, in deep convection in the SPNA (e.g.
108 Born and Mignot 2012). To explore this link, we define a separate index of abrupt change in the SPNA
109 based on mixed layer depths (MLDs). Given the varied locations and depths of simulated deep mixed
110 layers (Heuzé, 2021), for this index we use a model-based approach: we first calculate the wintertime
111 mean MLDs from the first 20 years of the simulation (or combined simulations) and then use as a
112 search region the area where these MLDs are greater than 400 metres. We use the first 20 years,
113 rather than the pre-industrial control run, to maximise data availability. We detect an abrupt-MLD
114 change where the decline in MLDs in this search region is greater than 45% of the mean over at least
115 50% of this region. While changes in some regions could be more significant than others, this
116 method gives no preference to the specific location of changes in MLDs. Ensemble members where
117 the time mean MLD area (greater than 400 metres) is less than 2×10^5 km² are discounted to exclude
118 abrupt changes that amount to only a few grid cells. In all cases, decadal changes are calculated
119 using an annually moving window. To avoid double counting, when multiple, consecutive events
120 would be detected – or events would overlap – only the event with greatest magnitude is selected.

121 **3 Results**

122 **3.1 Abrupt events in SST and MLD**

123 We begin by searching for events in the future projections under the 4 main scenarios (SSP1-2.6,
124 SSP2-4.5, SSP3-7.0, SSP5-8.5). For SSP1-2.6, we find 5 unique, abrupt events based on our SST index
125 and 5 events based on our MLD index out of 130 ensemble members (Supp. Text 1, Supp. Table 1).
126 Since our SST-based metric is similar to that used by SW21, this includes the events highlighted in
127 SW21 (Supp. Text 1). However, with only 5 events there is a little statistical power in our results. We
128 therefore extend our analysis to include the historical simulations from which the scenario
129 simulations were initiated.

130

131 **Figure 1. Area-averaged subpolar sea surface temperature (SST; A) and Mixed Layer Depth (MLD,**
 132 **model-specific regions; B) anomalies in all models and ensemble members in the concatenated**
 133 **historical and SSP1-2.6 scenario simulations (grey). Timeseries have a 10 year running mean**
 134 **applied. In each panel, events involving the variable of interest (SST/MLD) are shown in red, and**
 135 **events involving the other variable (MLD/SST) are shown in blue.**

136 Including the historical simulations increases the number of resultant abrupt events to 19 for the SST
 137 metric and 20 for the MLD metric from a total of 108 ensemble members (Figure 1 and Supp. Tables
 138 1 and 2). This includes previously undetected events that occur near the start of the scenario
 139 simulations. Figure 1 confirms that SST and MLD events are not co-located in time. Most of the MLD-
 140 based events occur around the year 2020 (Figure 1B), which is when the overall forcing and
 141 associated warming and mixed-layer shoaling trends are highest. Hence, many of the “abrupt” MLD
 142 events we see here could also be considered a part of an ongoing, sustained decline, rather than an
 143 individual event. This is in comparison to the SST-based events, many of which occur at times when
 144 the long-term SST trend is not strong (Figure 1A).

145 For SST-based events, the associated changes are shown in Figure 2 using composite maps. These are
 146 defined as the average difference from the preceding decade across all events, centred on the event.
 147 Along with a cooling of the SPNA (Figure 2F, H) there is a shallowing of the MLD in the Labrador Sea
 148 in the same and the preceding decade (Figure 2B, G). As such, there is a relationship between SST-
 149 based events and MLDs, although not with the abrupt MLD events identified previously, and not
 150 every SST event is associated with MLD shallowing (Figure 1B, Supp. Figure 2). This may be because
 151 our MLD event index picks up changes in the model’s preferred convection site, which is not the
 152 Labrador Sea in some models. The SST-based events also show a concomitant change in mean sea
 153 level pressure (MSLP, Figure 2J) consistent with an anomalously positive NAO index and signals of a
 154 negative NAO in the preceding decade (Figure 2E). In the decade following the event there is a
 155 warming of the SPNA, suggesting that the system is undergoing temporary decadal variability, rather
 156 than a sustained change (Figure 2K, M). For comparison, this warming is similar in magnitude and
 157 extent to the warming seen in the ensemble mean during the period of maximum warming (Supp.
 158 Figure 3).

159

160 In contrast to the composite picture, the four abrupt SST events that occur in the future do not
 161 appear to show decadal variability, but instead a more persistent temperature change. These events

162 appear to be associated with MLD shallowing (Supp. Figure 2, events #4, #5, #16, #20. Note that
 163 events #4 and #5 correspond to the two events highlighted in SW21).

164 In the MLD-based events, there is a general warming both before, during, and after the events (Supp.
 165 Figure 4). We suggest that the MLD-events are not driving the warming seen in those composites.
 166 Instead, long-term warming may contribute to increased stratification of the SPNA and associated
 167 capping of deep convection, which leads to a shallowing, and in some cases an abrupt change, in
 168 MLDs. The apparent lack of warming in the central SPNA would then be consistent with a
 169 competition between large-scale warming and local cooling (due to a weakening AMOC), which is the
 170 proposed mechanism behind the SPNA warming hole (Menary & Wood, 2018).

171

172 **Figure 2. Composite maps of Sea Surface Temperature (SST; first column), Mixed Layer Depth**
 173 **(MLD; second column), Surface Air Temperature (SAT; third column), precipitation (fourth column)**
 174 **and mean sea level pressure (MSLP; fifth column) for abrupt SST events in the combined historical**
 175 **plus SSP1-2.6 scenario simulations preceding the abrupt event (A-E), centred on the abrupt event**
 176 **(F-J), and following the abrupt event (K-O). Red titles denote the variable used to create the**
 177 **composite. Grid points where the data is not significant at the 95% level are masked. This was**
 178 **determined using bootstrapping: the same number of samples (19 for the combined simulations)**
 179 **were randomly selected from the entire dataset to create a composite, which was repeated to**
 180 **create a distribution from 10000 composites. Also highlighted are the regions used for subsequent**
 181 **lagged regression analysis (SST: F, MLD: G, NAO: crosses in J) and the regions defined as British Isles**
 182 **and Europe (H).**

183

184 **3.2 Proposed mechanisms**

185 Decadal to multidecadal variability of SPNA SSTs is mainly driven by changes in ocean circulation
 186 (Buckley & Marshall, 2016). Variability with ~20-year periodicity has been shown to be driven by
 187 internally generated Rossby waves which propagate from east to west (Sévellec and Fedorov 2013,
 188 Muir and Fedorov, 2017; Gastineau 2018). Here, multi-model composites of SSTs do not show signals
 189 of propagation (not shown) though it is possible that this mechanism is at play in individual models.

190 A different mechanism has also been proposed for multidecadal variability in the SPNA, with a
 191 prolonged positive phase of the NAO driving increased convection and deep-water formation in the
 192 northwest SPNA, resulting in a stronger ocean circulation (Eden and Jung 2001, Robson 2012, Yeager
 193 and Robson 2017). This drives increased northward ocean advection of heat and increased SSTs in
 194 the SPNA. A prolonged negative NAO results in cooler SSTs through the same mechanism. To explore
 195 this mechanism, we show lead-lag correlations using timeseries of the composite events (Figure 3).
 196 We use annual SST, wintertime MLD and NAO indices using the regions defined in Figure 2 (F, G, J),
 197 with MLD over the northwest SPNA used as a proxy for convection there.

198

199

200 **Figure 3. Lagged correlations between the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) and northwestern SPNA**
 201 **mixed layer depths (MLDs; A), sea surface temperatures (SSTs; B) and between MLDs and SSTs (C).**
 202 **Solid black lines denote correlations required for significance at the 90% level. Significance was**
 203 **estimated via a bootstrap approach by conducting the same lagged regressions on arbitrary**
 204 **composite time series.**

205 Results show that a negative NAO precedes a reduction in MLDs by around 7-9 years (Figure 3A, α)
 206 and a reduction in SSTs by around 9-10 years (Figure 3B, γ). This is broadly consistent with the lag
 207 between MLDs and SSTs, which is around 2-4 years (Figure 3C, ϵ).

208 Although we cannot assess the mechanisms in detail, the composite abrupt changes studied here
 209 show the same relationships between the NAO, SSTs, and northwestern SPNA MLDs as found in
 210 previous mechanistic studies. We therefore suggest that many abrupt SST cooling events in the SPNA
 211 (using our definition) could be the result of decadal-multidecadal variability in the coupled
 212 atmosphere-ocean system. These events may include a role for MLD changes, but not necessarily
 213 abrupt ones.

214 3.3 Impacts

215 Abrupt changes from the SST events are associated with climate anomalies in the British Isles (the
 216 highly populated region potentially most exposed to the SST events) and of Europe as a whole
 217 (Figure 2H). To put impacts in context with projected long-term warming, we show simulated British

218 Isles SAT changes under the historical plus SSP2-4.5 scenario as a plausible future pathway (UN
 219 Environment Programme, 2023) and superimpose the composite SST-event timeseries at arbitrary
 220 points in time for illustration (Figure 4). These composite events reveal a potentially important
 221 decadal cooling over the British Isles, followed by a warming (Figure 4A, blue). This cooling is
 222 statistically significant in comparison to both simulated and observed decadal timescale variability
 223 (Figure 4B), in both summer and winter as well as the annual mean (Supp. Figure 5A,B,C). The mean
 224 decadal cooling in the composites is -0.64°C , compared to -0.40 to 0.61°C (95% range) for all years in
 225 the simulations. Averaged over Europe, the decadal timescale changes in annual mean SAT are less
 226 significant, although substantial cooling is seen in the annual mean (Figure 4C, D) and particularly
 227 summer (Supp. Figure 5E).

228 Whilst the decadal timescale changes (associated with abrupt SST events) may be larger than the
 229 observed decadal timescale variability, they would not be enough to “reset” SAT over the British Isles
 230 to 20th century levels. Nevertheless, since a cooling trend is not currently being planned for, this
 231 could have implications for adaptation which is currently focussed on warming. Within 15 years the
 232 effect of the composite abrupt SST-event on SAT is largely undone. However, if combined with
 233 concomitant anthropogenic warming, this rebound could represent a significant and impactful local
 234 decadal warming trend over the British Isles. For example, assuming the warming rates are
 235 independent and adding this rebound phase ($0.39^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{decade}$) to the mean warming rate for the year
 236 2050 ($0.16^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{decade}$; from the full model ensemble using SSP2-4.5) yields a temporary local
 237 warming rate of $0.55^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{decade}$ for the British Isles. This is greater than the decadal British Isles
 238 warming rate in SSP5-8.5 for the same period ($0.39^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{decade}$) and more like the SSP5-8.5 rate
 239 towards the end of the 21st century (not shown). Note that the more persistent SST events show
 240 similar magnitudes of cooling in the British Isles to the shorter events, albeit longer lasting. (Supp.
 241 Figure 2)

242

243 **Figure 4. Surface air temperature (SAT) anomalies over the British Isles (A) and Europe (C) in**
 244 **observations (red) and CMIP6 models (historical plus SSP2-4.5 scenario simulations, shown as the**
 245 **ensemble mean and 1 and 2 standard deviations, black). The SAT from the sea surface temperature**
 246 **(SST) composites are shown in blue and overlaid at arbitrary years (trend-adjusted) to illustrate**
 247 **their magnitude relative to long term changes (shading represents 2 standard deviations). Also**

248 **shown are the distributions of decadal changes in SAT over the British Isles (B) and Europe (D) in**
249 **observations (red), CMIP6 models (black) and across the 19 member composites (the maximum**
250 **decadal change, i.e. corresponding to Figure 1; blue).**

251 The distribution of decadal timescale precipitation change associated with the SST-based events
252 shows smaller changes than SAT, with the British Isles seeing a shift towards larger decadal increases
253 in winter. Europe sees a slight shift towards larger decreases in summer (Supp. Figure 5).

254 For abrupt MLD changes, there is some signal of increased SAT (Supp. Figure 6), again consistent with
255 the overall warming trend in the abrupt MLD composites (Supp. Figure 4). Precipitation over the
256 British Isles shows a shift towards larger decadal decreases in winter and away from the largest
257 decadal increases in summer.

258 **Discussion**

259 We have investigated the occurrence of abrupt SST and MLD events in the SPNA in CMIP6 models in
260 historical and future scenarios. The larger set of model runs studied here, and our different
261 definitions used, have revealed a diversity of SST event types in the CMIP6 ensemble, including the
262 small number of persistent changes discussed by SW21 alongside a larger number of shorter-lived
263 changes (cf. Sgubin et al. 2017). Many abrupt SST events are associated with decadal timescale,
264 coupled variability, in which convection may play a role but does not change abruptly. On the other
265 hand, abrupt MLD events appear to be related to longer timescale anthropogenic warming.

266 To fully understand the risks from abrupt SPNA change it will be necessary to develop a more
267 complete documentation of possible types of event, and their drivers. It should also be noted that
268 dominant mechanisms of variability may be dependent on the underlying mean SPNA state, due to
269 either model biases (Menary et al. 2015) or the gradually changing background climate (Gu et al.
270 2024).

271 In Sgubin et al (2017) and SW21, models with better SPNA stratification were more likely to show
272 abrupt SST changes. Using our model-based definitions of mixing locations, we find no clear link
273 between the location or mean area of the mixed layers and whether a given model is more or less
274 likely to show an abrupt SST change (Supp. Figure 7). However, another important part of the
275 proposed mechanism driving abrupt SST changes is the NAO, whose statistics can be poorly
276 simulated in climate models (Davini & Cagnazzo, 2014). Supp. Figure 8 shows that ensemble
277 members with more realistic wintertime NAO variability are more likely to show both abrupt SST and
278 MLD events. Applying a simple Gaussian weighting (Supp. Text 2) increases the likelihoods of a given
279 ensemble member showing an abrupt SST (MLD) event before the year 2100 from 15% (18%) to 29%
280 (33%). Hence, as in SW21, constraining the models using relevant observations yields an increased
281 likelihood of abrupt changes.

282 **Summary and Conclusions**

283 Our analysis suggests that many SST events are consistent with decadal timescale variability in the
284 SPNA, linked to the NAO, and that they are not associated with an abrupt and sustained change in
285 MLDs. This apparent difference from SW21 is likely due to the different definition of SST events used
286 here, and possibly the larger sample of CMIP runs analysed. SW21 (and Sgubin et al 2017) define
287 events in terms of a 3 standard deviation departure from variability in a long control run, whereas we
288 use here a more observable definition based on an SST change of a defined magnitude. Our
289 algorithm does pick out the small number of persistent events that were the focus in SW21, as well
290 as a larger number of decadal-timescale, NAO-related events. For our MLD-based metric, abrupt

291 changes are associated with longer timescale, sustained *increases* in SST, and occur most often
292 during 2000-2040, when the subpolar warming rate due to anthropogenic climate change is largest.
293 It is possible that a differently defined metric of SPNA convection may identify different events. Given
294 the diversity of events found, it may therefore be beneficial for community-defined metrics to be
295 discussed and agreed upon.

296 Although the cooling associated with many SST-based events is temporary, it could nevertheless
297 represent a significant change in SAT over the British Isles, with the magnitude of the decadal change
298 comparable to the most extreme changes seen in observations or models. There have so far been
299 very few studies of the potential socioeconomic or ecological impacts of abrupt SPNA events (e.g.
300 Sgubin et al., 2019) although their presence in some CMIP5 and CMIP6 ensemble members means
301 that their effects may have already been included in the range of possible outcomes in impacts
302 studies that used these ensembles (Hasegawa et al., 2022). Both a period of cooling and a
303 subsequent rebound period with relatively rapid warming could pose challenges for adaptation.
304 Relatively cold temperatures could directly bring risks if adaptation plans have been based on
305 assumptions of ongoing warming. A relatively cool period could also potentially delay further
306 adaptation to ongoing warming by creating a false impression of a lack of a warming trend. If the
307 subsequent rebound of temperatures is more rapid than the previous long-term trend, the faster
308 rate of warming may be more difficult for ecosystems and society to adapt to. Further analysis
309 specifically focussing on impacts, across multiple socio-economic sectors, driven by simulations with
310 both temporary and persistent abrupt SPNA events, would be valuable.

311 We find that those models with a better representation of NAO variability are more likely to show
312 abrupt events. Further work should understand and quantify how the likelihood of abrupt events
313 depends on the fidelity of the models and the gradually evolving mean state (Menary et al 2015,
314 Sgubin et al. 2017, SW21, Gu et al. 2024). Finally, given the coupled nature of abrupt SST events and
315 their link to previous work in a decadal climate prediction context (Msadek et al., 2014; Robson et al.,
316 2012), it would be worthwhile to understand to what extent abrupt cooling is (or might be)
317 predictable.

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323 **Open Research**

324 The CMIP data are available through ESGF's website at <https://esgf-node.llnl.gov/search/cmip6/>. The
325 BEST data are available through the Berkeley Earth website at <https://berkeleyearth.org/data/>. The
326 HadSLP2 data are available through the UK Met Office website at
327 <https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/hadobs/hadslp2/>. The GPCP data are available through the Deutscher
328 Wetterdienst website at
329 https://opendata.dwd.de/climate_environment/GPCP/html/download_gate.html.

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